

Still Passing the Buck: Macroeconomic and Fiscal Performance of Argentine Administrations, 1853–2025

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Abstract

We rank all 41 Argentine national administrations that governed between 1853 and 2025 with the two indices proposed by della Paolera, Irigoin, and Bózzoli (2003) — the Classical Macroeconomic Performance Index (CMPI) and the Fiscal Pressure Index (FPI) — and their combined Overall Index, scoring each government by the macroeconomic and fiscal improvement it delivered over the situation it inherited. A single percentile pool of 173 annual observations places every administration, from the mid-nineteenth-century Confederation to the 2024–25 stabilization, on a common scale. Extending the original 1853–1999 analysis through 2025 requires confronting documented distortions in modern Argentine statistics: we catalogue twenty-one manipulation and accounting practices, correct the affected series from independent and reproducible sources, and bound the judgment-dependent cases with sensitivity variants. On the restricted 1853–1999 pool the replication of the original rankings is almost exact (Spearman $\rho = 0.997$ for the FPI, 0.952 for the CMPI). In the unified ranking Menem (1990–95) leads the CMPI and the Overall Index. Consolidating the central bank’s quasi-fiscal debt into the public debt stock and valuing output at the free-market exchange rate during exchange-control years materially reorders the modern fiscal ranking. The long-run results confirm the original *passing-the-buck* thesis: administrations bought macroeconomic calm with debt — on the Treasury’s books or hidden in the central bank — and passed the bill to their successors.

Keywords: Argentina; economic history; macroeconomic performance; fiscal policy; inflation; public debt; statistical manipulation.

JEL classification: C43; E31; E62; H63; N16; O54.

1 Introduction

How to read the indices. The CMPI and FPI measure *improvement* relative to the situation inherited from the previous administration — not absolute levels. Component scores are percentiles of annual innovations pooled over all 173 years: a score of 0.90 means the administration’s average annual improvement sat in the top 10 percent of all improvements recorded since 1853. Rank 1 is best. See Section 3 for the formulas and three structural caveats, Section 7 for robustness, and the Glossary (Appendix E) for terminology.

How well did each Argentine government manage the economy it inherited? The question dominates Argentine public debate, yet it is usually argued with absolute outcomes

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— inflation under one president against inflation under another — which conflates what a government did with what it received. della Paolera, Irigoin, and Bózzoli (2003) proposed a comparative answer: score each administration by the *improvement* it delivered over the macroeconomic and fiscal situation bequeathed by its predecessor, and rank all administrations on a common percentile scale. Their Classical Macroeconomic Performance Index (CMPI) aggregates inflation, devaluation, the hard-currency interest rate, and per-capita growth; their Fiscal Pressure Index (FPI) adds the management of the intertemporal budget constraint; the average of the two is an Overall Index. Applied to 33 administrations over 1853–1999, the framework produced the central finding the authors summarized in their title: Argentine governments repeatedly bought contemporaneous macroeconomic calm with fiscal pressure that they passed to their successors.

This paper extends the complete two-index framework to the full 1853–2025 span — 41 administrations and a percentile pool of 173 annual observations — placing the original 33 historical terms and the eight administrations of 2000–2025 on a single, internally consistent scale. The extension is not a mechanical appending of recent data. Between 2007 and 2015 the national statistical institute (INDEC) understated consumer-price inflation by a factor of roughly three to four and overstated real growth, episodes that led to the first declaration of censure in the history of the International Monetary Fund ([International Monetary Fund 2013](#); [Cavallo 2013](#); [Coremberg 2017](#)). Exchange controls in 2012–15 and 2019–25 pinned the official exchange rate far below the free-market rate. Successive governments accumulated remunerated central-bank liabilities — a quasi-fiscal debt exceeding ten percent of GDP at its peaks — that appears in no Treasury debt statistic. Any ranking that ingests official series uncritically reproduces these distortions. A second, subtler problem is internal to the methodology: annual-average exchange rates produce wrong-signed devaluation innovations around mid-year devaluations, an artefact that affects the historical sample as well as the modern one.

Our contributions are four. First, we construct corrected 1853–2025 series for the nine variables behind the two indices, documenting every known statistical manipulation and accounting practice that materially affects them — a twenty-one-entry catalogue (Section 4, Appendix B) stating the direction of each bias and its treatment. Corrections enter the baseline only when an independent, reproducible source exists (alternative price indices, free-market exchange quotations, revised national accounts, central-bank balance sheets); judgment-dependent adjustments enter only as sensitivity variants, reported whichever administration they favour. Second, we resolve the annual-average devaluation artefact by using December-quotation exchange-rate series for the entire sample. Third, we extend the FPI with two corrections to the modern debt-stock components: a free-market revaluation of GDP during exchange-control years, and the consolidation of the central bank’s remunerated liabilities into the public debt stock. Fourth, we validate the implementation by replicating the original published rankings on the restricted 1853–1999 pool, obtaining Spearman rank correlations of 0.997 (FPI) and 0.952 (CMPI) against the original Table 3.4.

The headline results place Menem (1990–95) first on the CMPI and the Overall Index, with the 2024–25 stabilization and Obligado’s 1854–56 reforms close behind, and crisis terms at the bottom — consistent with the original finding that durable hard-currency and convertible stabilizations score highest. The fiscal corrections are decisive for the modern ranking: once the central bank’s hidden debt is consolidated and the exchange-control distortion removed, the administrations that *built up* quasi-fiscal liabilities fall to the bottom of the FPI, while the 2024–25 consolidation registers as a sharp reduction in fiscal pressure rather than the spurious increase shown by the raw Treasury series. The long-run picture confirms the *passing-the-buck* dynamic over 173 years.

The paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 situates the contribution in the literature. Section 3 presents the methodology. Section 4 describes the data and the corrections. Section 5 reports the rankings. Section 6 validates the implementation against the original study. Section 7 reports robustness exercises. Sections 8–10 discuss interpretation, limitations, and conclusions. A complete replication package accompanies the paper (Appendix A).

2 Related literature

The paper extends della Paolera, Irigoien, and Bózzoli (2003), chapter 3 of *A New Economic History of Argentina* (della Paolera and Taylor 2003), which built the CMPI and FPI for 1853–1999. The long-run quantitative history of Argentine money and finance on which that chapter rests includes della Paolera and Taylor (2001) on the currency-board era, della Paolera (1994) and Cortés Conde (1989) on nineteenth-century monetary and fiscal experiments, Irigoien (2000) and Amaral (1988) on the early inflationary-finance period, and the long statistical series compiled by Ferreres (2010). General economic histories of the period include Gerchunoff and Llach (1998) and Rapoport (2000).

The measurement problems of modern Argentine statistics have their own literature. Cavallo (2013) documents the 2007–2015 INDEC consumer-price intervention using online prices; Cavallo and Rigobon (2016) generalize the methodology; Coremberg (2017) quantifies the parallel overstatement of real output growth; the IMF’s declaration of censure (International Monetary Fund 2013) is the institutional landmark. Our contribution to this strand is practical: a documented, reproducible mapping from each known distortion to its effect on a long-run performance ranking — including the quasi-fiscal liabilities and exchange-control wedges that standard debt and exchange-rate series omit.

The theoretical background of the indices — seigniorage and the inflation tax, the intertemporal budget constraint, and currency-crisis contagion — is the classical one (Sargent 1986; de Fiore 2000; Ennis 2007; Eichengreen, Rose, and Wyplosz 1996).

Two further strands frame the interpretation. The fiscal-dominance tradition descending from Sargent and Wallace (1981) supplies the mechanism behind the *passing-the-buck* finding: when the fiscal authority does not internalize the intertemporal budget constraint, the monetary authority eventually finances the gap, and inflation becomes a fiscal phenomenon. The comparative project of Kehoe and Nicolini (2021) applies exactly this lens to eleven Latin American countries; its Argentina chapter (Buera and Nicolini 2021) reads six decades of inflation, default, and stabilization as the monetary consequence of persistent fiscal imbalance — the regional pattern of which Argentina is the extreme case, and the same dynamic the FPI traces administration by administration. On the political-economy side, Spiller and Tommasi (2007) document why the dynamic persists: Argentine institutions give policymakers unusually short horizons and weak technologies for enforcing intertemporal agreements, so costs shifted past one’s own term are heavily discounted. Finally, the treatment of central-bank operations as fiscal policy in disguise follows the public-finance tradition of Mackenzie and Stella (1996); the modern Argentine remunerated-liability stock that Section 4 consolidates is documented in the IMF’s program reports (International Monetary Fund 2022).

3 Methodology

3.1 The Classical Macroeconomic Performance Index

The CMPI aggregates four classical variables: **inflation**, linked to the government’s high-powered-money policy and seigniorage; **devaluation**, the willingness to defend the external value of the currency; the **real interest rate on hard currency**, a proxy for country risk and external credit tightness; and **per-capita growth**, the administration’s influence on the pace of real activity.

For each variable and year we compute the **innovation**: the value in that year minus the value in the *last year of the previous administration* — the inherited, or “legacy,” condition. Each annual innovation is converted to a percentile rank across all O years in the pool using the original Appendix A formula $R = (O - o)/O$, where o is the innovation’s position in the ranking (best = 1): the best innovation in the pool scores $(O - 1)/O \approx 0.994$ and the worst scores 0. An administration’s CMPI is the average of its four percentile scores over its term; higher is better. Inflation and devaluation enter as continuously compounded rates $\ln(1 + x)$, which prevents extreme episodes from dominating the index.

To be concrete: a year in which inflation fell from an inherited 40 percent to 10 percent produces an innovation of roughly -0.36 log-points. This scores near the top of the percentile distribution and contributes to a high CMPI *regardless of whether 10 percent is “low” in absolute terms*. The comparative design is what makes the index informative about governance rather than about inherited luck.

3.2 The Fiscal Pressure Index

The CMPI captures contemporaneous performance, but for a peripheral economy with recurrent debt crises this is insufficient. The FPI ranks administrations by their management of the intertemporal budget constraint, built on the first-order difference equation for the debt ratio that drives the original study’s transversality condition:

$$\frac{B_t}{Y_t} = \frac{1 + r_t}{1 + g_t} \frac{B_{t-1}}{Y_{t-1}} + \frac{DEF_t}{Y_t},$$

where B/Y is the debt-to-GDP ratio, r the real interest rate, g the growth rate, and DEF the primary deficit. The FPI aggregates five indicators, each scored exactly like the CMPI as an innovation percentile: **debt/GDP** (the burden relative to activity), **debt/exports** (the burden relative to repayment capacity), **primary result/revenues** (net fiscal management, discounting inherited debt service), **primary result/debt service** (resources available to service the debt), and $(1 + r)/(1 + g)$ (the amplifying factor on the debt ratio; values above one mean the debt ratio grows automatically even with a balanced primary budget). High indebtedness or an unbalanced budget is a “hot potato” passed to successors; the opposite is a positive externality future governments inherit.

Following the original Table 3.4, the **Overall Index** ranks administrations by the simple average of their CMPI and FPI scores. The exact formulas behind every step — innovations, percentile assignment, aggregation, and the two debt-stock corrections — are collected in Appendix D.

3.3 How to read the ranking: three structural caveats

The method has three properties that every reader should hold in mind. They are features of the original design, applied uniformly to all 41 administrations — not data corrections, and not fixable without changing what the index measures.

1. **Improvement is not the end state.** The index scores each year against the situation *inherited*, averaged over the term — not the state in which an administration leaves the country. A term that inherits a catastrophe and stabilizes it scores high even if absolute conditions remain poor; a term that inherits calm and ends in crisis scores low even if its average year was comfortable. Section 8 discusses the clearest modern case.
2. **Term averages favour short corrective shocks.** Stabilizations front-load their best macroeconomic years, so a two-year term can outscore four-to-six-year terms that include later decay. Section 7 re-scores every administration on its first two years only, putting partial terms on an equal footing.
3. **Single-year inherited baselines amplify V-shaped shocks.** Because every year of a term is measured against the predecessor's *last* year, a collapse-and-rebound pair inside one term (COVID: -10.3 percent per-capita growth in 2020, $+10.2$ percent in 2021) is lightly penalized on the way down and fully rewarded on the way back. Section 7 includes a variant that drops 2020–21 from the percentile pool.

3.4 Administration boundaries

The 41 terms follow the original intervals exactly where the two studies overlap (33 terms, 1853–1999), including the rule of assigning each year to whoever ruled the larger part of it. Conventions carried over from the original study: single-year caretaker terms are kept separate when conventionally distinguished (Alsina 1853, Uriburu 1931, Guido 1962–63); military juntas are presented as one term (1976–83); civilian transition periods with rapid turnover are combined. For 2000–2025, beyond the original span, 2001–03 is split as De la Rúa (to 2001) and Duhalde (2002–03) to separate the crisis trough from the stabilization — the single deliberate exception to the majority-of-year rule, which keeps the post-default stabilization program in one piece. The 2024–25 term is partial by construction and is decomposed year by year in Section 6. A sensitivity experiment merging the shortest one-year terms into their neighbours moved only bottom CMPI ranks and left the top ten and all FPI and Overall top-five positions unchanged.

4 Data

4.1 Two data regimes

The series combine two regimes. For 1852–1963 we use the original authors' annual dataset (`data_a_2018.xlsx`) directly: inflation and devaluation as annual log-differences, per-capita growth, and the four fiscal ratios. Interest rates use the published term averages of the original Table 3.1, since the dataset contains no annual interest series; the 1852 baseline is derived from the original Table 3.2. For 1964–2025 we use annual values from the World Bank World Development Indicators ([World Bank 2025](#)), INDEC price and national-accounts series, the EMBIG Argentina country-risk spread from 1998 ([Banco Central de Reserva del Perú 2025](#)), total Sector Público Nacional gross debt from the Secretaría de Finanzas ([Secretaría de Finanzas, Ministerio de Economía 2025](#)), and budget execution from the national open-data portal ([datos.gob.ar 2025](#)). Free-market exchange-

rate quotations for the exchange-control years come from public APIs ([ArgentinaDatos 2025](#)) and the December-quotation devaluation series for 1960–1999 from Ruíz (1990) and the original dataset.

Figure 1 maps data reliability by year and variable; the full lineage of every series is documented in the replication package.

Figure 1: Data reliability by year and variable across the nine index inputs. Letters grade source quality; the catalogue in Appendix B documents every flagged episode.

4.2 Statistical integrity: known manipulations and their treatment

An honest comparison of Argentine administrations must confront a hard fact: several governments distorted the statistics themselves, or used fiscal and monetary accounting that flatters the headline numbers while shifting costs off the books. Appendix B catalogues every such practice known to materially affect the nine variables behind the CMPI and FPI — twenty-one entries spanning 1931–2025 — stating for each the direction of the bias and its treatment here.

The treatment discipline is uniform. **Corrected** practices are fixed in the baseline series, with the official series kept as an audit column and an official-versus-corrected comparison chart beside each correction, so the size of the distortion is visible rather than asserted. **Sensitivity** practices involve judgment-dependent estimates, so they enter as documented memo columns and re-ranked variants — never silent baseline changes — reported whichever administration they favour. **Documented** practices are outside the nine index variables or not confidently quantifiable, and are flagged for the reader. No adjustment relies on the say-so of any government, including the current one.

Four corrections carry the baseline:

Consumer prices, 2007–2015. The INDEC intervention understated inflation roughly three- to four-fold; the episode ended in the IMF censure ([International Monetary Fund 2013](#)) and a criminal conviction of the responsible Commerce Secretary. The baseline replaces 2007–2015 official inflation with the average of alternative indices (IPC Congreso, San Luis, CABA, Santa Fe), consistent with the online-price evidence of Cavallo ([2013](#)). Figure 2 shows the official series against the alternatives.

Real output growth, 2007–2015. The base-1993 national accounts overstated volume growth (2008 official +6.8 versus revised +3.1 percent; 2009 +0.9 versus –5.9). The World Bank series used here embed INDEC’s 2016 revision, whose cumulative 2008–15 correction matches the independent ARKLEMS reconstruction ([Coremberg 2017](#)). Figure 3 compares the vintages.

Devaluation: December quotations for the full sample. Annual-average exchange rates blend pre- and post-devaluation months, producing wrong-signed innovations around mid-

Figure 2: Official INDEC consumer-price inflation versus alternative provincial and private indices, 2007–2015. The baseline uses the alternative average; the official series is retained as an audit column.

Figure 3: Official base-1993 real growth versus the 2016-revision series, 2005–2015.

year devaluations. We use December quotations for the entire 1853–2025 span: the original authors’ series to 1999 (which embeds the free-market *dólar libre* of Ruíz (1990) for 1960–89), then December BCRA wholesale rates in free years and December free-market (CCL/blue) averages in exchange-control years from 2000. Section 6 shows that this choice reproduces the original published devaluation innovations exactly for the four terms affected by mid-year devaluations.

Exchange-control wedges. During the *cepo* years (2012–15, 2019–25) the official rate was administratively pinned with a free-market premium that reached 100 percent. Measuring the regime by its deeds rather than its words (Levy Yeyati and Sturzenegger 2005), devaluation uses free-market December averages (Figure 4); the fiscal corrections below remove the parallel distortion of the dollar-valued GDP in the debt ratios.

Figure 4: Official versus free-market (CCL/blue) exchange rate during the exchange-control years; the premium (“brecha”) reached 100 percent.

4.3 Two corrections to the modern debt stock

The FPI’s two debt-stock components require corrections that no official series provides.

First, the **exchange-control revaluation**: during *cepo* years the dollar-valued GDP in the debt/GDP denominator is inflated by the artificially low official rate. The correction revalues output at the free-market rate, bounded from below by a conservative variant that assumes only half the debt stock is foreign-currency-linked, and complemented by a variant using the measured currency composition of the debt (Section 7).

Second, the **consolidation of quasi-fiscal debt**: from 2002 the central bank sterilized monetary emission with remunerated liabilities (Lebac/Nobac, then Leliq, then Pases) that repeatedly exceeded ten percent of GDP — economically public debt, but absent from every Treasury statistic. The correction adds the measured year-end stock (BCRA statistical-API series, December observations) to the public debt of 2003–2025. Figure 5 shows the layered debt stock; Figure 6 shows the associated quasi-fiscal interest flow, which never enters the Treasury’s primary result.

Table 1 summarizes both corrections by administration. The corrections are decisive for the modern fiscal ranking (Section 5), and symmetric: they penalize the administrations that accumulated hidden liabilities and credit those that consolidated them, whichever side of

the political spectrum either falls on.

Table 1: Exchange-control factor and central-bank quasi-fiscal debt by administration (term means). “Cepo x” is the free-market/official revaluation factor applied to dollar GDP; “BCRA % GDP” is the remunerated-liability stock consolidated into public debt.

Administration	Years	Debt/GDP off.	Cepo x	BCRA % GDP	Debt/GDP adj.
Duhalde	2002-2003	1.630	1.000	1.712	1.647
N.Kirchner	2004-2007	0.843	1.000	5.404	0.897
C.Kirchner	2008-2011	0.454	1.000	4.270	0.497
C.Kirchner II	2012-2015	0.453	1.397	4.563	0.680
Macri	2016-2019	0.670	1.025	7.217	0.760
Fernandez	2020-2023	0.703	1.857	11.387	1.403
Milei	2024-2025	0.703	1.184	0.013	0.836

Figure 5: Public debt layers, 2001–2025: official Treasury stock, exchange-control revaluation, and consolidated central-bank remunerated liabilities.

The same discipline governs the primary-balance components: one-off revenues booked above the line (pension-fund nationalization flows, SDR allocations, tax amnesties, export-duty advances) and accounting practices that flatter the cash result (unpaid interest during default, capitalizing instruments in 2024–25) are documented per-row with sources, and enter re-ranked sensitivity variants (Section 7). Figure 7 contrasts the official and structural primary results.

5 Results

5.1 Contemporaneous macroeconomic performance

The CMPI ranking of all 41 administrations is reported in Table 2. Menem (1990–95) ranks first, the 2024–25 stabilization second, and Obligado (1854–56) third; the bottom of the table collects the crisis terms — Alsina (1853) last, preceded by Guido (1962–63) and the second Cristina Kirchner term (2012–15), with the hyperinflation endgame of Alfonsín (1984–89) close behind.

Figure 6: The quasi-fiscal flow: central-bank interest on remunerated liabilities, which enters no Treasury primary result.

Figure 7: Official versus structural primary result: one-off and accounting-driven revenues removed.

Table 2: The Classical Macroeconomic Performance Index, all 41 administrations, 1853–2025. Component columns are mean innovation percentiles over the term; the pool is 173 annual observations.

Administration	Rank	Years	Regime	Inflation	Devaluation	Interest	Growth	CMPI
Menem	1	1990–1995	Modern	0.975	0.980	0.858	0.812	0.906
Milei	2	2024–2025	Modern	0.514	0.928	0.974	0.598	0.754
Obligado	3	1854–1856	Historical	0.784	0.778	0.520	0.915	0.750
Menem II	4	1996–1999	Modern	0.676	0.610	0.957	0.676	0.730
Perón II	5	1952–1955	Historical	0.880	0.871	0.546	0.436	0.684
Justo	6	1932–1937	Historical	0.342	0.831	0.720	0.805	0.675
Sarmiento	7	1869–1874	Historical	0.432	0.554	0.928	0.663	0.644
Roca	8	1881–1886	Historical	0.917	0.310	0.754	0.504	0.621
Mitre	9	1860–1868	Historical	0.401	0.435	0.798	0.665	0.575
Ramírez/Farrell	10	1943–1945	Historical	0.547	0.607	0.601	0.472	0.557
Onganía	11	1967–1969	Modern	0.684	0.663	0.145	0.699	0.548
Pellegrini	12	1891–1892	Historical	0.592	0.688	0.384	0.520	0.546
Yrigoyen	13	1917–1922	Historical	0.681	0.490	0.332	0.680	0.546
Peron III	14	1973–1975	Modern	0.528	0.303	0.832	0.516	0.545
Avellaneda	15	1875–1880	Historical	0.403	0.508	0.298	0.954	0.540
Videla/Viola/Galtieri/Bignone	16	1976–1983	Modern	0.576	0.871	0.182	0.502	0.533
N.Kirchner	17	2004–2007	Modern	0.513	0.178	0.968	0.465	0.531
Ortiz/Castillo	18	1938–1942	Historical	0.686	0.295	0.890	0.250	0.530
Sáenz Peña R./de la Plaza	19	1911–1916	Historical	0.613	0.579	0.627	0.243	0.515
Quintana/Figueroa	20	1905–1910	Historical	0.432	0.544	0.668	0.224	0.467
Aramburu	21	1956–1957	Historical	0.260	0.864	0.396	0.329	0.462
Fernandez	22	2020–2023	Modern	0.431	0.623	0.092	0.561	0.427
Perón I	23	1946–1951	Historical	0.321	0.213	0.454	0.719	0.427
De la Rúa	24	2000–2001	Modern	0.416	0.529	0.251	0.500	0.424
Roca II	25	1899–1904	Historical	0.471	0.329	0.488	0.400	0.422
Juárez Celman	26	1887–1890	Historical	0.386	0.341	0.251	0.689	0.417

Administration	Rank	Years	Regime	Inflation	Devaluation	Interest	Growth	CMPI
Frondizi	27	1958–1961	Historical	0.415	0.403	0.367	0.442	0.407
Yrigoyen II	28	1929–1930	Historical	0.630	0.358	0.408	0.228	0.406
Illia	29	1964–1966	Modern	0.497	0.133	0.272	0.713	0.404
Uriburu JF	30	1931–1931	Historical	0.480	0.341	0.422	0.353	0.399
Macri	31	2016–2019	Modern	0.395	0.423	0.421	0.316	0.389
Alsina II	32	1857–1859	Historical	0.538	0.620	0.231	0.067	0.364
Sáenz Peña L./Uriburu JE	33	1893–1898	Historical	0.141	0.382	0.575	0.296	0.349
C.Kirchner	34	2008–2011	Modern	0.575	0.412	0.082	0.286	0.339
Levingston/Lanusse	35	1970–1972	Modern	0.185	0.108	0.694	0.197	0.296
Alfonso	36	1984–1989	Modern	0.396	0.448	0.026	0.274	0.286
De Alvear	37	1923–1928	Historical	0.278	0.357	0.118	0.378	0.283
Duhalde	38	2002–2003	Modern	0.116	0.410	0.003	0.523	0.263
C.Kirchner II	39	2012–2015	Modern	0.366	0.146	0.276	0.228	0.254
Guido	40	1962–1963	Historical	0.237	0.390	0.217	0.075	0.230
Alsina	41	1853–1853	Historical	0.104	0.145	0.416	0.000	0.166

5.2 Fiscal pressure

Table 3 reports the FPI. Obligado (1854–56) leads, with the 2024–25 term second and Roca II (1899–1904) third. The two debt-stock corrections of Section 4.3 drive the modern reordering: the 2023 inherited baseline carries both the peso overvaluation (a factor near two) and some thirteen percent of GDP in central-bank debt at the December 2023 year-end, against which the 2024–25 consolidation and record primary surplus register as a sharp *reduction* in fiscal pressure — rather than the spurious debt increase shown by the raw Treasury series — while the administrations that grew the quasi-fiscal stock (2020–23 and 2012–15) fall to the bottom of the table. Néstor Kirchner (2004–07) remains high on the FPI because the 2005 restructuring — among the deepest haircuts in the modern sovereign-debt record ([Sturzenegger and Zettelmeyer 2008](#)) — cut the far larger Treasury debt even as sterilization began: the consolidation captures the build-up without letting it overwhelm a genuine deleveraging.

Table 3: The Fiscal Pressure Index, all 41 administrations. Components are innovation percentiles of debt/GDP, debt/exports, primary result/revenues, primary result/debt service, and $(1+r)/(1+g)$.

Administration	Rank	Years	Debt / GDP	Debt / Exp	Res / Rev	Res / DebtSv	$(1+r) / (1+g)$	FPI
Obligado	1	1854–1856	0.696	0.696	0.967	0.936	0.929	0.845

Administration	Rank	Years	Debt / GDP	Debt / Exp	Res / Rev	Res / DebtSv	(1+r) / (1+g)	FPI
Milei	2	2024–2025	0.945	0.737	0.740	0.838	0.818	0.816
Roca II	3	1899–1904	0.716	0.895	0.962	0.888	0.417	0.776
N.Kirchner	4	2004–2007	0.941	0.970	0.480	0.500	0.877	0.753
Menem	5	1990–1995	0.968	0.561	0.629	0.609	0.838	0.721
Perón I	6	1946–1951	0.795	0.961	0.740	0.297	0.685	0.695
Avellaneda	7	1875–1880	0.819	0.549	0.515	0.501	0.952	0.667
Mitre	8	1860–1868	0.324	0.389	0.905	0.969	0.695	0.656
Yrigoyen	9	1917–1922	0.601	0.773	0.636	0.611	0.618	0.648
Uriburu JF	10	1931–1931	0.630	0.780	0.751	0.682	0.347	0.638
Onganía	11	1967–1969	0.480	0.403	0.663	0.848	0.561	0.591
Videla/Viola/Galtieri/Bignone	12	1976–1983	0.416	0.232	0.879	0.876	0.405	0.562
Sarmiento	13	1869–1874	0.266	0.401	0.559	0.693	0.697	0.523
Illia	14	1964–1966	0.491	0.486	0.445	0.435	0.647	0.501
Menem II	15	1996–1999	0.399	0.630	0.363	0.322	0.772	0.497
Frondizi	16	1958–1961	0.676	0.595	0.428	0.328	0.400	0.486
Sáenz Peña L./Uriburu JE	17	1893–1898	0.803	0.528	0.357	0.350	0.352	0.478
Aramburu	18	1956–1957	0.595	0.572	0.460	0.422	0.335	0.477
C.Kirchner	19	2008–2011	0.795	0.757	0.269	0.360	0.198	0.476
Quintana/Figueroa	20	1905–1910	0.804	0.802	0.159	0.226	0.320	0.462
Pellegrini	21	1891–1892	0.127	0.419	0.552	0.656	0.465	0.444
De Alvear	22	1923–1928	0.304	0.497	0.562	0.582	0.275	0.444
Levingston/Lanusse	23	1970–1972	0.426	0.659	0.326	0.455	0.316	0.436
Perón II	24	1952–1955	0.384	0.158	0.422	0.697	0.471	0.426
Justo	25	1932–1937	0.253	0.104	0.467	0.466	0.814	0.421
Sáenz Peña R./de la Plaza	26	1911–1916	0.290	0.549	0.405	0.477	0.311	0.406
Alfonsín	27	1984–1989	0.286	0.189	0.843	0.633	0.066	0.403
Macri	28	2016–2019	0.514	0.377	0.389	0.402	0.306	0.398

Administration	Rank	Years	Debt / GDP	Debt / Exp	Res / Rev	Res / DebtSv	(1+r) / (1+g)	FPI
De la Rúa	29	2000–2001	0.298	0.564	0.355	0.376	0.361	0.391
Peron III	30	1973–1975	0.451	0.638	0.067	0.110	0.582	0.370
Roca	31	1881–1886	0.549	0.366	0.132	0.182	0.559	0.358
Ortiz/Castillo	32	1938–1942	0.607	0.117	0.280	0.298	0.434	0.347
Ramírez/Farrell	33	1943–1945	0.364	0.584	0.116	0.148	0.522	0.347
Guido	34	1962–1963	0.434	0.896	0.133	0.092	0.104	0.332
Yrigoyen II	35	1929–1930	0.630	0.344	0.199	0.228	0.257	0.332
Juárez Celman	36	1887–1890	0.124	0.210	0.312	0.279	0.620	0.309
C.Kirchner II	37	2012–2015	0.116	0.223	0.288	0.347	0.221	0.239
Alsina II	38	1857–1859	0.210	0.514	0.195	0.177	0.083	0.236
Duhalde	39	2002–2003	0.003	0.127	0.503	0.486	0.017	0.227
Fernandez	40	2020–2023	0.032	0.301	0.214	0.133	0.368	0.210
Alsina	41	1853–1853	0.017	0.110	0.000	0.017	0.006	0.030

5.3 The Overall Index

Table 4 combines the two indices. Menem (1990–95) remains first, Obligado second, and the 2024–25 term third. The joint reading exposes the central *passing-the-buck* dynamic: administrations with a high CMPI rank paired with a low FPI rank bought macroeconomic calm with debt — on the Treasury’s books or hidden in the central bank — and handed the bill to their successors. The 2024–25 term is unusual in the modern era for ranking in the top tier on both dimensions, with the caveats of Sections 6 and 8: the term is partial, and two measurement conventions that favour it are flagged symmetrically with the Kirchner-era corrections.

Table 4: The Overall Index: average of CMPI and FPI scores, with component ranks and a Borda-count cross-check.

Administration	Rank	Years	CMPI Rank	FPI Rank	CMPI	FPI	Overall	Borda Rank
Menem	1	1990–1995	1	5	0.906	0.721	0.814	3
Obligado	2	1854–1856	3	1	0.750	0.845	0.797	1
Milei	3	2024–2025	2	2	0.754	0.816	0.785	2
N.Kirchner	4	2004–2007	17	4	0.531	0.753	0.642	7
Mitre	5	1860–1868	9	8	0.575	0.656	0.616	4

Administration	Rank	Years	CMPI Rank	FPI Rank	CMPI	FPI	Overall	Borda Rank
Menem II	6	1996–1999	4	15	0.730	0.497	0.613	5
Avellaneda	7	1875–1880	15	7	0.540	0.667	0.604	8
Roca II	8	1899–1904	25	3	0.422	0.776	0.599	11
Yrigoyen	9	1917–1922	13	9	0.546	0.648	0.597	9
Sarmiento	10	1869–1874	7	13	0.644	0.523	0.583	6
Onganía	11	1967–1969	11	11	0.548	0.591	0.569	10
Perón I	12	1946–1951	23	6	0.427	0.695	0.561	13
Perón II	13	1952–1955	5	24	0.684	0.426	0.555	14
Justo	14	1932–1937	6	25	0.675	0.421	0.548	15
Videla/Viola/Galtieri/Bignone	15	1976–1983	16	12	0.533	0.562	0.547	12
Uriburu JF	16	1931–1931	30	10	0.399	0.638	0.518	19
Pellegrini	17	1891–1892	12	21	0.546	0.444	0.495	16
Roca	18	1881–1886	8	31	0.621	0.358	0.489	17
Aramburu	19	1956–1957	21	18	0.462	0.477	0.470	18
Quintana/Figueroa	20	1905–1910	20	20	0.467	0.462	0.465	20
Sáenz Peña R./de la Plaza	21	1911–1916	19	26	0.515	0.406	0.461	25
Peron III	22	1973–1975	14	30	0.545	0.370	0.457	24
Illia	23	1964–1966	29	14	0.404	0.501	0.452	21
Ramírez/Farrell	24	1943–1945	10	33	0.557	0.347	0.452	22
Fronzizi	25	1958–1961	27	16	0.407	0.486	0.446	23
Ortiz/Castillo	26	1938–1942	18	32	0.530	0.347	0.439	26
Sáenz Peña L./Uriburu JE	27	1893–1898	33	17	0.349	0.478	0.413	27
De la Rúa	28	2000–2001	24	29	0.424	0.391	0.407	28
C.Kirchner	29	2008–2011	34	19	0.339	0.476	0.407	29
Macri	30	2016–2019	31	28	0.389	0.398	0.393	31
Yrigoyen II	31	1929–1930	28	35	0.406	0.332	0.369	35
Levingston/Lanusse	32	1970–1972	35	23	0.296	0.436	0.366	30

Administration	Rank	Years	CMPI Rank	FPI Rank	CMPI	FPI	Overall	Borda Rank
De Alvear	33	1923–1928	37	22	0.283	0.444	0.363	32
Juárez Celman	34	1887–1890	26	36	0.417	0.309	0.363	33
Alfonsín	35	1984–1989	36	27	0.286	0.403	0.345	36
Fernández	36	2020–2023	22	40	0.427	0.210	0.318	34
Alsina II	37	1857–1859	32	38	0.364	0.236	0.300	37
Guido	38	1962–1963	40	34	0.230	0.332	0.281	38
C.Kirchner II	39	2012–2015	39	37	0.254	0.239	0.246	39
Duhalde	40	2002–2003	38	39	0.263	0.227	0.245	40
Alsina	41	1853–1853	41	41	0.166	0.030	0.098	41

6 Validation against the original study

The implementation is validated against three benchmarks.

Replication of the published rankings. Restricting the percentile pool to 1853–1999 removes the pool-expansion effect, so any deviation from the original Table 3.4 reflects only the two known data differences (flat within-term interest averages, and WDI-sourced inflation and growth for 1964–99). On this restricted pool the FPI reproduces the original fiscal ranking with Spearman $\rho = 0.997$ and the CMPI with $\rho = 0.952$. The devaluation convention is validated term by term: the December-quotation series reproduces the original published Table 3.2 devaluation innovations to the decimal for the four administrations that followed mid-year devaluations (Illia, Onganía, Perón III, and the 1976–83 junta), where annual-average data produce the wrong sign.

Cross-notebook consistency. The companion modern-period implementation shares five identically defined terms with this notebook over 1964–1999. The Spearman correlation across the five is 0.90: the four terms unaffected by data-convention changes preserve their relative order exactly, and the single deviation (Illia) is by design — the December-quotation correction of Section 4.2 applied to its inherited 1963 devaluation baseline.

Decomposition of the partial 2024–25 term. Table 5 decomposes the 2024–25 years against the first two Menem years. The structure is the corrective-shock one: a first year dominated by the devaluation and interest components against a hyper-distressed inherited baseline, and a second year in which the disinflation component takes over. The comparison bounds the interpretation of a partial term: on a first-two-years basis (Section 7) the 2024–25 program and the Menem stabilization are statistically adjacent.

Table 5: Year-by-year CMPI decomposition: the partial 2024–25 term versus the first two years of the Menem stabilization.

Year	Administration	Inflation	Devaluation	Interest	Growth	CMPI
2024	Milei	0.081	0.931	0.971	0.503	0.621
2025	Milei	0.948	0.925	0.977	0.694	0.886
1990	Menem (first 2 yrs)	0.936	0.965	0.867	0.665	0.858
1991	Menem (first 2 yrs)	0.971	0.971	0.873	0.913	0.932

7 Robustness

Rank stability under resampling. Across 1,000 bootstrap resamples of the pool years, the CMPI medians hold Menem first (10–90 percent band 1–1; first in 98 percent of draws), the 2024–25 term in band 2–8 (top five in 74 percent of resamples), and Obligado in band 2–4.

Sensitivity variants. Every judgment-dependent adjustment is re-ranked and reported whichever administration it favours: the cepo revaluation under measured currency composition and under the conservative 50 percent lower bound (Table 6); accrued interest during the 2002–05 default and the holdout add-back; the 2024–25 capitalizing-interest rescaling; the structural primary balance with one-offs removed; the paired importer-arrears and BOPREAL add-back; contingent liabilities (the YPF judgment and Paris Club arrears); the 1977–90 quasi-fiscal stock, which bounds the asymmetry that otherwise flatters the 1980s terms relative to 2003–25; a 1946–59 parallel-premium overlay for the historical exchange controls; alternative inflation indices including a CABA-index variant for 2024–25; and a no-COVID pool variant. None of the variants displaces the top of the Overall ranking; the largest movements are within the modern FPI block, documented case by case in the replication package.

Table 6: FPI rank sensitivity for the focus administrations under the exchange-control and growth-definition variants.

Administration	Baseline	Measured FX share	50% FX share	Total-growth r/g
Obligado	1	1	1	1
Milei	2	2	2	2
Roca II	3	3	3	3
N.Kirchner	4	4	4	4
Menem	5	5	5	5
Macri	28	29	30	28
C.Kirchner II	37	37	37	37
Fernandez	40	40	40	40
Duhalde	39	39	39	39

Component weights. The equal weighting of components is the original study’s convention; the component-exclusion variants bound its impact as extreme weight perturbations. Menem remains first with the interest dimension removed entirely, while the 2024–25 term falls from second to fifth — the country-risk collapse is a material part of its score — and Obligado falls from third to fifth when inflation, its coarsest pre-1866 proxy dimension, is removed.

Term length. Re-scoring every administration on its first two years only (Table 7) puts partial and complete terms on an equal footing and confirms that the term-average design, not data choices, drives the strong showing of short corrective terms.

Table 7: Full-term versus first-two-years CMPI ranks, selected administrations.

Administration	Full-term rank	First-2-years rank
Menem	1	1
Milei	2	2
Obligado	3	3
Menem II	4	4
Justo	6	5
Perón II	5	6
Roca	8	7
Peron III	14	8
Sarmiento	7	9
Ramírez/Farrell	10	10
Sáenz Peña R./de la Plaza	19	11
Macri	31	12

Bootstrap confidence intervals and pairwise comparisons. Table 8 reports 95 percent confidence intervals for the bootstrap rank distributions of the focus administrations, computed from 1,000 shared-draw resamples of the pool years (the same resample drives all three indices, so cross-index and pairwise statements are internally consistent). Menem remains ahead of the 2024–25 term on the CMPI in 97.6 percent of draws — a one-sided bootstrap p of 0.024 — while on the Overall Index the two are statistically adjacent (Menem ahead in 69 percent of draws, $p = 0.31$), and Obligado leads the 2024–25 term on the FPI in 75 percent ($p = 0.25$). All three podium administrations remain in the Overall top five in every draw; N. Kirchner does so in 76 percent, and the bottom-ranked modern terms never reach it.

Table 8: Bootstrap rank distributions, 1,000 resamples of the pool years: median rank and 95 percent confidence interval per index, and the share of draws in which the administration stays in the Overall top five. Statistics are computed over the draws in which the term’s years appear in the resample.

Administration	CMPI median	CMPI 95% CI	FPI median	FPI 95% CI	Overall median	Overall 95% CI	P(top 5)
Menem	1	1–1	5	3–8	1	1–3	100%
Milei	3	2–10	2	1–4	3	1–3	100%
Obligado	3	2–5	1	1–2	2	1–3	100%
Roca II	25	15–34	3	1–5	9	4–15	16%
N.Kirchner	15	10–20	4	2–6	5	3–8	76%
Fernandez	24	10–36	37	33–40	34	23–39	0%

8 Discussion

The 173-year unified ranking reproduces the main findings of the original study for the historical period while placing the 2000–2025 administrations on the same scale. Stabilizations anchored to hard-currency or convertible regimes score highest — Menem’s Convertibility first in both the original and here; Obligado’s 1854–56 reforms, which ended decades of inflationary finance, near the top — and crisis terms score lowest. The 2024–25 disinflation scores highly even in this long-run context.

Three interpretive points deserve emphasis.

What the index measures. The CMPI rewards improvement relative to the inherited year, averaged over the term — not the state in which an administration leaves the country. The clearest modern case is the Fernández (2020–23) versus Macri (2016–19) inversion: Macri had lower absolute inflation, devaluation, and country risk, yet ranks just below Fernández, because Macri inherited the calm, exchange-control-pinned 2015 economy and bequeathed the 2019 crisis against which Fernández is then scored each year (for an insider account of the 2016–19 program and its collapse, see [Sturzenegger 2019](#)). COVID amplifies the inversion through the V-shaped 2020–21 pair. This is an artefact of the single-year inherited baseline — a design feature, disclosed and bounded in Section 7 — and the ranking should be read alongside the contemporaneous record (Appendix C).

Why the data corrections are decisive. Four adjustments determine the credibility of the modern ranking: the alternative price indices stop the 2007–2015 intervention from inflating the affected scores; the country-risk spread removes a fabricated interest improvement in 2020–23 and exposes the 2024–25 collapse in country risk; the December-quotation devaluation series fixes the wrong-signed innovations around mid-year devaluations; and the two debt-stock corrections keep the fiscal components from mismeasuring the 2003–2025 terms in both directions.

The passing-the-buck reading. Administrations that pair a high CMPI with a low FPI purchased calm with future resources. The quasi-fiscal channel is the modern refinement of the original thesis: where the nineteenth-century version of the dynamic ran through Treasury debt and suspension of convertibility, the twenty-first-century version runs through the central bank’s balance sheet — invisible in the official debt statistics that the original authors could take at face value for their period.

Why the buck keeps being passed. The index documents the pattern; it does not by itself explain its persistence over 173 years, and nothing in a percentile rank identifies the constraints a given administration faced. The political-economy literature supplies the candidate mechanism: Spiller and Tommasi (2007) show that Argentine institutions — short and uncertain tenures, a federal fiscal commons, weak legislative and judicial enforcement of intertemporal bargains — systematically shorten policymakers’ horizons, making debt, visible or hidden, the cheapest instrument with which to buy the present. Read through Buera and Nicolini (2021), the FPI is the administration-level trace of the fiscal dominance that the comparative Latin American literature identifies at the level of regimes ([Kehoe and Nicolini 2021](#)). These are interpretations consistent with the ranking, not findings of it.

9 Limitations

The principal limitations, each documented in the replication package and bounded by a sensitivity variant where feasible:

- **Historical interest rates (1852–1997) use published term averages**, so historical administrations have flat within-term interest variation; with WDI-sourced 1964–99 inflation and growth, this is the main remaining source of divergence from the original ranking ($\rho = 0.952$).
- **Data-regime seam at 1963/64** for inflation and growth; devaluation has no seam; interest switches from term averages to the EMBIG spread in 1998. The modern interest dimension is a *spread*, not a rate level, so innovations crossing the 1997/98 seam embed a small level shift.

- **The FPI's $(1+r)/(1+g)$ uses per-capita growth** (the only annual series available across the full span) where the original defines g as total growth; innovations difference out slow-moving population growth almost entirely, and the total-growth variant moves every focus rank by at most one position (Table 6).
- **The exchange-control revaluation assumes a foreign-currency-linked debt stock**; the measured-composition and 50-percent variants bound the correction from both sides.
- **The quasi-fiscal consolidation starts in 2003** and uses measured December year-end stocks from the central bank's statistical API for 2002–2024 (the curated anchors that previously carried the series are retained as cross-checks); 2025 and the 1977–90 extension rest on documented estimates, the latter entering only as a sensitivity variant.
- **A debt-definition seam at 2018/19**: the historical ratios use the original central-government concept, the 2019–25 extension uses total Sector Público Nacional gross debt.
- **Pool non-comparability**: adding eight modern terms changes every historical percentile; the full-pool ranking is an extension, not a reproduction, of the original 33-term table. The single 173-year pool is nonetheless deliberate: one common yardstick is what allows a Confederation presidency and a twenty-first-century stabilization to be ranked at all. Era-specific sub-pools would re-score every administration against its own era's standards — undoing the cross-era comparability the index exists to provide — while introducing arbitrary regime break points; standardized (z-score) scoring was rejected because hyperinflation-era tails would dominate any variance-based scale. Percentile ranks over one pool are the design that survives both objections.
- **The single-last-year inherited baseline is likewise a convention**. Averaging several pre-term years would dilute one-off shocks in the inherited year, but it would also smear the predecessor's own crisis into the benchmark a government is judged against, weakening the question the index asks. The V-shaped-shock caveat of Section 3.3 and the no-COVID pool variant of Section 7 disclose and bound the principal consequence.
- **Equal component weights are the original study's convention**; the component-exclusion variants of Section 7 act as extreme weight perturbations and bound the impact of this choice on the focus ranks.
- **The indices measure macroeconomic and fiscal management only**. Distributional outcomes, poverty, productivity, and institutional quality are outside the nine variables; an administration can rank highly here while performing poorly on those dimensions, and conversely. The ranking is one input to an overall assessment of a government, not a verdict.
- **Two 2024–25 measurement caveats work in the current administration's favour** and are flagged symmetrically with the Kirchner-era corrections: cash-basis results exclude capitalizing interest, and the 2004–05-basket CPI understates the services-led relative-price normalization. Both are bounded by variants (Section 7).

10 Conclusion

Applying both indices of della Paolera, Irigoin, and Bózzoli (2003) across the full 1853–2025 span places all 41 Argentine national administrations on a single, internally consistent scale. The method's logic — judging each government by the macroeconomic and fiscal improvement it delivers over the situation it inherited — puts durable hard-currency and convertible stabilizations at the top and crises, and the terms that bequeath them, at the bottom. The unified ranking reproduces the original historical results almost exactly on the restricted pool while extending them through 2025 with corrected data: alternative price indices for the 2007–2015 statistical intervention, a country-risk spread for the modern interest series, free-

market exchange rates for the control years, December-quotation devaluations throughout, and — for the fiscal dimension — an exchange-control revaluation and the consolidation of the central bank’s quasi-fiscal debt.

The Overall Index confirms the original *passing-the-buck* thesis over the long run: administrations that purchased macroeconomic calm with debt — on the Treasury or hidden in the central bank — handed the bill to their successors. Making the hidden half of that debt visible is, we would argue, the precondition for any honest scoreboard of Argentine economic governance.

Reproducibility

Appendix A. The complete replication package — the analysis notebook, all input data with documented lineage, download and generation scripts, an input validator, unit tests, and continuous integration that re-executes the full pipeline — is available at <https://github.com/jahnog/still-passing-the-buck>. Every table and figure in this paper is extracted programmatically from the executed notebook by the build script (`scripts/build_paper.py`), so prose and pipeline cannot silently diverge. Data vintages are stamped in the package; baseline-affecting revisions are logged. An archived snapshot of the paper and the replication package is deposited at Zenodo: [doi:10.5281/zenodo.20651731](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20651731).

The statistical-integrity catalogue

Appendix B. The full twenty-one-entry catalogue, with per-row sources, is maintained in the replication package; the condensed version follows. “Corrected” practices are fixed in the baseline (official series kept as audit columns); “Sensitivity” practices enter re-ranked variants only; “Documented” practices are flagged for the reader.

Table 9: The statistical-integrity catalogue (condensed). Full entries with affected terms, magnitudes, and per-row sources are in the replication package.

#	Practice	Period	Bias	Treatment
1	INDEC CPI intervention (under-stated 3–4x)	2007–15	Inflation down	Corrected
2	GDP volume overstatement, base-1993 accounts	2007–15	Growth up	Corrected
3	GDP-warrant payouts on overstated growth	2009–14	Fiscal flows (both)	Documented
4	Exchange controls (cepo), official rate pinned	2012–15, 2019–25	Devaluation, debt/GDP down	Corrected
5	Historical exchange controls and parallel premia	1931–59	Devaluation down	Sensitivity
6	“Surplus” while in default (unpaid interest)	2002–05	Result/debt-service up	Sensitivity
7	Holdout debt excluded from official stock	2005–15	Debt down	Sensitivity
8	CER under-indexation of inflation-linked debt	2007–15	Debt, interest down	Documented
9	Pension nationalization booked as revenue	2008–15	Result/revenue up	Sensitivity
10	Reserve hollowing; paper profits as revenue	2006–15, 2021–23	Result/revenue up	Sensitivity
11	Hidden central-bank debt stock (Lebac/Leliq/Pases)	2002–24	Debt down	Corrected
12	Hidden central-bank deficit (quasi-fiscal flow)	2004–24	Result up	Sensitivity
13	1980s Cuenta de Regulación Monetaria	1984–89	Debt down, result up	Sensitivity

#	Practice	Period	Bias	Treatment
14	One-off revenues above the line (SDR, amnesties)	various	Result/revenue up	Sensitivity
15	Importer arrears / BOPREAL conversion	2022–25	Debt down, then up	Sensitivity
16	Cash surplus excluding capitalizing interest	2024–25	Result up	Sensitivity
17	CPI basket vintage (2004–05 weights)	2017–25	Inflation down	Sensitivity
18	Price controls; repressed inflation to successor	several	Incumbent inflation down	Documented
19	Statistics blackouts; labour-data masking	2002–16	Non-index inputs	Documented
20	Crisis balance-sheet transfers (1982, 1989, 2002)	as listed	Debt up (real)	Documented
21	Contingent liabilities (YPF judgment, Paris Club)	2002–25	Debt down	Sensitivity

The contemporaneous record

Appendix C. For the reader who wants the absolute outcomes alongside the innovation-based ranking, the table below reports term-average inflation, devaluation, interest, and growth for all 41 administrations.

Table 10: Contemporaneous (absolute) term averages, all 41 administrations. This is the record against which the caveat of Section 3.3 should be read.

Administration	From	To	Inflation	Devaluation	Interest	Growth
Alsina	1853	1853	14.11	14.11	15.19	-17.53
Obligado	1854	1856	3.19	3.19	14.10	7.15
Alsina II	1857	1859	0.53	0.53	15.72	-4.82
Mitre	1860	1868	1.68	2.08	12.70	7.43
Sarmiento	1869	1874	4.33	0.00	8.63	2.30
Avellaneda	1875	1880	10.01	2.24	10.02	5.19
Roca	1881	1886	-2.94	3.25	7.22	8.08
Juárez Celman	1887	1890	12.06	15.46	8.79	5.40
Pellegrini	1891	1892	10.86	12.15	9.72	-4.43
Sáenz Peña L./Uriburu JE	1893	1898	-1.23	-4.12	8.22	0.72
Roca II	1899	1904	-1.72	-1.76	7.32	3.82
Quintana/Figueroa	1905	1910	4.97	0.04	5.50	2.43
Sáenz Peña R./de la Plaza	1911	1916	3.71	0.06	3.73	-3.99
Yrigoyen	1917	1922	1.03	2.70	5.08	3.10
De Alvear	1923	1928	0.09	-2.72	8.63	2.94
Yrigoyen II	1929	1930	-3.67	7.47	8.77	-2.45
Uriburu JF	1931	1931	-3.31	23.26	8.72	-9.22
Justo	1932	1937	3.98	-0.62	6.02	1.88
Ortiz/Castillo	1938	1942	4.52	4.55	2.09	0.77
Ramírez/Farrell	1943	1945	5.57	-1.46	0.52	0.77
Perón I	1946	1951	20.93	31.58	-0.02	2.72
Perón II	1952	1955	10.25	7.19	-1.25	0.89
Aramburu	1956	1957	20.93	1.64	-0.49	2.21
Fronzizi	1958	1961	34.67	20.15	0.46	2.31
Guido	1962	1963	26.05	24.42	2.89	-2.41
Illia	1964	1966	21.68	22.50	4.39	5.02
Onganía	1967	1969	13.35	9.24	7.64	4.29
Levingston/Lanusse	1970	1972	31.16	40.28	5.48	1.83

Administration	From	To	Inflation	Devaluation	Interest	Growth
Peron III	1973	1975	58.84	79.67	2.44	1.12
Videla/Viola/Galtieri/Bignone	1976	1983	107.37	94.51	5.15	-0.28
Alfonsin	1984	1989	173.14	181.46	17.38	-2.04
Menem	1990	1995	65.75	33.73	14.26	2.86
Menem II	1996	1999	-0.94	0.00	8.17	2.29
De la Rúa	2000	2001	0.69	0.00	11.12	-3.68
Duhalde	2002	2003	27.51	54.27	56.19	-2.06
N.Kirchner	2004	2007	13.56	1.47	20.67	7.64
C.Kirchner	2008	2011	19.49	7.80	8.57	2.49
C.Kirchner II	2012	2015	25.90	30.43	8.58	-0.62
Macri	2016	2019	30.64	40.93	6.88	-1.80
Fernandez	2020	2023	54.12	64.00	20.54	0.87
Milei	2024	2025	72.38	22.90	10.59	1.26

Index construction: exact formulas

Appendix D. This appendix states the complete scoring algebra; it matches the implementation in the replication package (`scripts/cmpi_core.py`) line for line.

Terms and innovations. Let administration j govern years f_j, \dots, l_j , and let $x_{v,t}$ denote the value of variable v in year t . Inflation and devaluation enter as continuously compounded rates, $x = \ln(1 + \pi)$. Every year of the term is scored against the same inherited benchmark — the last year of the predecessor:

$$\Delta_{v,t} = x_{v,t} - x_{v,f_j-1}, \quad t = f_j, \dots, l_j.$$

Percentile assignment. Innovations are pooled across all $O = 173$ years (1853–2025). For each variable, the innovation in position o of the favourable-to-unfavourable ordering (best = 1) receives the percentile score of the original Appendix A:

$$R_{v,t} = \frac{O - o_{v,t}}{O} \in \left[0, \frac{O-1}{O}\right].$$

Favourable means *lower* for inflation, devaluation, the real interest rate, and the three FPI debt and amplification variables, and *higher* for growth and the two FPI primary-result variables.

Aggregation. An administration's component score is the mean percentile over its term years, and each index is the unweighted mean of its components ($n = 4$ for the CMPI, $n = 5$ for the FPI):

$$\text{CMPI}_j = \frac{1}{4} \sum_{v \in \mathcal{C}} \frac{1}{T_j} \sum_{t=f_j}^{l_j} R_{v,t}, \quad \text{FPI}_j = \frac{1}{5} \sum_{v \in \mathcal{F}} \frac{1}{T_j} \sum_{t=f_j}^{l_j} R_{v,t}$$

with $\mathcal{C} = \{\text{inflation, devaluation, interest, per-capita growth}\}$ and $\mathcal{F} = \{\text{debt/GDP, debt/exports, primary result/revenues, primary result/debt service, } (1+r)/(1+g)\}$. The Overall Index is $\frac{1}{2}(\text{CMPI}_j + \text{FPI}_j)$.

Debt dynamics. The FPI components derive from the first-order difference equation for the debt ratio,

$$\frac{B_t}{Y_t} = \frac{1 + r_t}{1 + g_t} \frac{B_{t-1}}{Y_{t-1}} + \frac{DEF_t}{Y_t},$$

whose amplification factor $(1 + r_t)/(1 + g_t)$ enters the FPI directly.

The two modern debt-stock corrections. During exchange-control years the official rate overstates dollar GDP, so the debt ratio is revalued at the free-market rate:

$$\left(\frac{B}{Y}\right)^{\text{cepo}} = \frac{B}{Y}_{\text{official}} \times \frac{e_{\text{parallel}}}{e_{\text{official}}},$$

and the central bank's remunerated liabilities are consolidated into the stock:

$$\left(\frac{B}{Y}\right)^{\text{adj}} = \left(\frac{B}{Y}\right)^{\text{cepo}} + \frac{\text{BCRA remunerated liabilities}}{Y}.$$

Structural primary result (sensitivity variant). Where one-off revenues are a share o of total revenues, the structural ratio is

$$\left(\frac{\text{Result}}{\text{Rev}}\right)^{\text{structural}} = \frac{R - o}{1 - o}.$$

Glossary

Appendix E. Terms used throughout the paper, in alphabetical order.

Administration (term) The unit of analysis: one of the 41 government intervals of 1853–2025 (Section 3.4). Each year of a term is scored against the last year of the predecessor.

Brecha (parallel premium) The percentage gap between the free-market and the official exchange rate during exchange-control years; it reached 100 percent in the modern cepos.

CCL / blue The two free-market dollar quotations used for the control years: the *contado con liquidación* rate (implicit in dual-listed securities) and the informal cash (“blue”) rate.

Cepo Colloquial name for Argentina's exchange-control regimes (2012–15 and 2019–25), under which the official rate was administratively pinned below the free-market rate.

CMPI Classical Macroeconomic Performance Index: the average innovation percentile across inflation, devaluation, the hard-currency real interest rate, and per-capita growth (Section 3.1).

Convertibility The 1991–2001 currency-board regime pegging the peso one-to-one to the US dollar.

December quotations The exchange-rate convention used throughout: year-end (December) rates rather than annual averages, which blend pre- and post-devaluation months and produce wrong-signed innovations (Section 4.2).

FPI Fiscal Pressure Index: the average innovation percentile across debt/GDP, debt/exports, primary result/revenues, primary result/debt service, and the debt-amplification factor $(1 + r)/(1 + g)$ (Section 3.2).

- INDEC intervention** The 2007–2015 manipulation of the official consumer-price index (and the parallel overstatement of real growth), which led to the IMF’s declaration of censure; corrected in the baseline with alternative indices (Section 4.2).
- Innovation** The annual value of a variable minus its value in the last year of the previous administration — the inherited condition (Section 3.1).
- Overall Index** The simple average of an administration’s CMPI and FPI scores.
- Percentile pool** The single pool of 173 annual observations (1853–2025) over which each variable’s innovations are ranked; the innovation in position o scores $(O - o)/O$.
- Primary result** The fiscal balance before interest payments; “structural” variants remove one-off revenues booked above the line.
- Quasi-fiscal debt** The central bank’s remunerated liabilities (Lebac/Nobac, Leliq/Notaliq, Pases) — economically public debt but absent from Treasury statistics; consolidated into the debt stock for 2003–2025 (Section 4.3).

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